

Differences in coauthorship and journal selection between prolific literature and music authors

Yu-Wei Chang¹ and Hsuan-Tung Yeh²

¹yuweichang2013@ntu.edu.tw, ²b08106006@ntu.edu.tw

^{1,2}Department of Library and Information Science, National Taiwan University, Taipei (Taiwan)

Introduction

Coauthorship is a feasible strategy for increasing publication output (Lee & Bozeman, 2005). Prolific authors outside of the disciplines of humanities tend to publish collaborative papers (Ding, 2010). We investigated whether prolific humanities researchers also adopt coauthorship as a publishing strategy, thus challenging the stereotypical notion that humanities researchers prefer single authorship.

Journal selection is crucial for humanities researchers because journal articles are the primary type of humanities publication (Ossenblok et al., 2014), and getting articles published in high-level journals is important for holding high positions at institutes and obtaining research funding. However, publishing articles in high-level journals is challenging (Runde, 2021). Because coauthorship improves research quality (Baji et al., 2021), we investigated whether coauthorship boosts researchers' confidence in submitting their articles to high-level journals. Furthermore, each coauthor takes different responsibilities. The first author is generally regarded as the author that made the largest contribution and effort. We further investigated whether prolific humanities researchers avoided being the first author in their coauthored articles to be able to allocate more time to their other studies.

Productivity and research quality are associated with coauthorship, journal level, and author role. Publication productivity varies across humanities disciplines (Ossenblok et al., 2014). Furthermore, publications within a particular discipline may be written by researchers from other disciplines (external researchers) (Singh et al., 2021). To verify the aforementioned research questions, in this study, we focused on two disciplines of humanities: literature and music. We compared the most prolific (top 100) literature and music authors in terms of the following four characteristics: rate of coauthorship, ratio of first-author articles to coauthored articles, selection of preferred journals, and disciplines of prolific authors.

Methods

Given the low publication output in humanities research, a relatively long period is necessary to evaluate the productivity of humanities researchers (Yair et al., 2022). In this study, we identified the 100 most prolific (per discipline) authors who published articles in Scopus-indexed literature and

music journals. Scopus was used as the data source because of its extensive coverage of journals across disciplines, accurate disambiguation of author names, and availability of journals' percentile rankings. Journals assigned the subject category "literature" and "music" were defined as literature and music journals, respectively.

We selected the 100 most prolific authors on the basis of their numbers of articles published in literature journals during 2001–2020. Another 100 most prolific authors were then selected on the basis of their numbers of articles published in music journals during the aforementioned period. The bibliographic records (2001–2020) of the 200 total authors (100 for each discipline) were downloaded. In addition, we recorded the percentile ranks of the journals in which the prolific authors published their articles. The percentile rank data are updated annually; thus, such data were obtained considering the year of the article's publication. The discipline of each prolific author was determined on the basis of the main discipline of the departments or institutes the authors were most affiliated with during the study period.

Results

Coauthorship rate

As shown in Table 1, the average number of articles per prolific author was higher in the discipline of literature than in that of music (27.2 vs. 18.3, respectively). The within-discipline differences in the productivity of the prolific authors were larger in music than in literature. Because the proportion of coauthored articles was considerably lower in literature than in music (9.2% vs. 75.8%, respectively), the first-authorship rate was calculated considering only coauthored articles. A higher proportion of first-author articles was observed in literature than in music (64.5% vs. 30.1%, respectively). The lower proportion of coauthored articles in literature was supported by a smaller average number of authors per article within this discipline. An independent samples *t* test revealed a significant difference in the average number of authors per article ($t[2,134.3] = 37.92; p < .05$) between music (mean \pm standard deviation, 2.69 ± 1.67) and literature (1.16 ± 0.58).

Table 1. Characteristics of articles stratified by discipline.

	Literature	Music
Total number of articles (Average)	2717 (27.2)	1831 (18.3)
Range (SD)	17–85 (14.6)	12–117 (11.4)
Coauthorship rate	9.2%	75.8%
Range (SD)	0–100 (23.2)	0–100 (25.7)
First-authorship rate	64.5% (162/251)	30.1% (419/1388)
Average number of authors per article	1.16	2.69

SD, standard deviation.

Journal preference

As illustrated in Figure 1, prolific literature authors most commonly published articles in journals at the lowest level (L4), whereas prolific music authors preferred to publish in the top 25% of journals (L1). A chi-square test indicated significant differences between the two disciplines in terms of the proportions of articles published in journals at four levels ($\chi^2 [3, N = 4,369] = 2117.27; p < .05$).

Figure 1. Proportion of articles (stratified by discipline) published in journals at the four levels.

Articles by external authors

As shown in Figure 2, the primary affiliation of most prolific literature authors was with a literature-related department or institute (internal authors, 67), whereas that of >50% of the 100 prolific music authors was with a non-music-related department or institute (external authors, 57). Most literature articles were single-authored articles published by internal authors, whereas most music articles were collaborative articles contributed to by internal authors. A chi-square test revealed significant differences between the two disciplines in terms of the proportion of articles (single author vs. coauthored and external authors vs. internal authors; $\chi^2 [3, N = 4,548] = 2,136.17; p < .05$).

Figure 2. Numbers of music and literature articles stratified by discipline of author affiliation and authorship pattern.

Conclusions

Prolific music authors appear to prefer coauthorship, a non-first-author role in coauthored articles, and high-level journals; these characteristics are different from those of prolific literature authors. The common characteristic of the two disciplines was a considerable proportion of external authors included in top 100 most prolific authors, particularly within the discipline of music. Because the high proportion of external authors in music may have been influenced by the wide scope of music journals, including journals related to acoustics engineering and computer science, future studies should consider journals' subject categories during journal selection.

Acknowledgments

This work was financially supported by the Ministry of Science and Technology (MOST), Taiwan, under Grant No. MOST 111-2410-H-002 -013 -MY2

References

- Baji, F., Mostafavi, I., Parsaei-Mohammadi, P., & Sabaghinejad, Z. (2021). Partnership ability and co-authorship network of information literacy field. *Scientometrics*, *126*(9), 8205–8216.
- Ding, Y. (2010). Semantic web: Who is who in the field: A bibliometric analysis. *Journal of Information Science*, *36*(3), 335–356.
- Lee, S., & Bozeman, B. (2005). The impact of research collaboration on scientific productivity. *Social Studies of Science*, *35*(5), 673–702.
- Ossenblok, T. L. B., Verleysen, F. T., & Engels, T. C. E. (2014). Coauthorship of journal articles and book chapters in the social sciences and humanities (2000-2010). *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, *65*(5), 882–897.
- Runde, B. J. (2021). Time to publish? Turnaround times, acceptance rates, and impact factors of journals in fisheries science. *PLoS ONE*, *16*(9), e0257841. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0257841>.
- Singh, V. K., Singh, P., Karmakar, M., Leta, J., & Mayr, P. (2021). The journal coverage of Web of Science, Scopus and Dimensions: A comparative analysis. *Scientometrics*, *126*(6), 5113–5142.
- Yair, G., Goldstein, K., Rotem, N., & Olejniczak, A. J. (2022). The three cultures in American science: publication productivity in physics, history and economics. *Scientometrics*, *127*(6), 2967–2980.